

FOOD ADDITIVES - TOXIC EFFECTS ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Abstract: This article focuses on food additives and their composition to examine how additives present in ultra-processed foods affect health. In addition, common food additives used in the food industry and their potential threats will be reviewed. In many cases, it has been proven that sodium benzoate, vitamin C, vitamin E, yellow No. 5 and yellow No. 6 really have an effect on human health. Other types of supplements that are found in nature have no significant association with cancer and health problems.

Keywords: food additives, food, consequences of food additives, E-group additives.

Introduction: With the development of the food industry, public concern has arisen regarding the safety of the use of artificial additives. Ultra-processed foods are made by adding additives such as antioxidants, preservatives and colors to change the properties of the food product and meet customer needs [V]. Today, a set of substances called food additives of group E can be found on the packaging of almost all food products. The buyer chooses products without always reading their composition. Food additives improve the quality of raw materials of the final product, the timing and preservation of the product - they simplify various production processes [II]. Preservatives significantly increase the shelf life of the product. But at the same time, food additives have a negative effect on the human body which manifests itself in various diseases. There are many different preservatives such as: flavorings, taste and smell enhancers, sweeteners. What does the letter “E” mean? To save space on food labels, Europe introduced a coding system for food additives in

1953. Instead of long chemical names, they began to use the letter "E" with digital codes. The first number after the letter "E" indicates the group to which the food additive belongs, according to the International Classification System (INS) [IV]. For example:

- E100 - E182 – dyes that enhance the color of the product.
- E200 - E299 - preservatives (extend the shelf life of the product), chemical sterilizing additives, protect against microbes, fungi, bacteriophages
- E300 - E399 - antioxidants (slow down oxidation, for example, color changes; similar in effect to preservatives)
- E400 - E499 - stabilizers (maintain the desired consistency of the product), thickeners - increase viscosity
- E500 - E599 - emulsifiers (maintain a homogeneous mixture of immiscible products, such as water and oil), similar in effect to stabilizers [III]

Thus, the letter "E" on the label indicates the presence of food additives that have been identified and classified according to the INS system. Each country sets its own standards for food additives, especially those that may be harmful to human health. Many acceptable levels of food additives are lower than in other countries. It is appropriate to talk about the dangers of some food additives that negatively affect the livelihoods of the population of Uzbekistan [I]. There are consequences of exposure to food additives, the manifestation of carcinogenic, mutagenic and other biological effects. This means that some food additives contained in imported foods may exceed acceptable levels and potentially cause:

- Gastrointestinal diseases
- Allergic reactions
- Oncological diseases (in case of carcinogens)

Therefore, it is important to be aware of the potential risks associated with consuming imported foods and to read labels carefully, paying attention to the presence of food additives. If you are in doubt about the safety of a food product, it is best to consult a doctor or nutritionist.

The goal of studying food additives is to understand the chemical properties of food additives in order to educate people about the real harmful ingredients in ultra-processed foods and avoid taking large doses.

Material and methods: Based on literature data, an analysis of the effect of food additives on the human body was carried out.

Results and methods: During the study, all products were divided into the following groups according to the degree of harmfulness.

Group 1: Carbonated drinks

High sugar content (up to 25 tablespoons of sugar per 1 liter in the case of Coca-Cola) can lead to problems with the pancreas, diabetes and obesity. Phosphoric acid (E338) in Coca-Cola can damage tooth enamel and internal organs. Sodium benzoate (E211) in carbonated drinks is a carcinogen at high doses. Aspartame (E951) can cause manic depression, panic attacks, and decreased intelligence. High dye content also poses a health hazard.

Group 2: Chips, crackers, croutons

High fat content, flavorings and additives can cause digestive problems and kill the taste of healthy foods. Acrylamide, which is formed when chips are fried, is a potentially carcinogenic substance. Monosodium glutamate (E621) may cause headaches, nausea, and allergic reactions in some people.

Group 3: Chewing gums

- Cheap chewing gums may contain the dangerous additive E129, which can cause allergic reactions.
- E330 supplement may increase the risk of cancer at high concentrations.
- Dye E102 can provoke asthma attacks.
- Even popular chewing gums such as Orbit, "Dirol" and "Stimorol" contain harmful food additives that can cause digestive upsets, allergies, nausea and liver disease.

Group 4: Candy Caramel

- Contains a large number of harmful food additives, dyes, preservatives and antioxidants.

Group 5: Chocolate products

- M&M's contain dangerous dyes that can cause asthma attacks, allergies and nausea.
- "Nesquik", "Nuts" and "KitKat" bars are considered safer as they contain mainly lecithin (E476), which is used to save expensive cocoa butter.

Group 6: Packaged cookies

Harmful food additives E503, 341 were found in Choco Pie cookies, causing stomach upset. It turns out that domestically produced chocolate products and cookies turned out to be the safest, and no harmful additives were found in yogurt at all.

After analyzing the composition of the products, we compiled a table of harmful food additives, where they were classified by degree of danger.

Dangerous - E102, E110, E120, E129, E503

Carcinogens - E124, E211, E330

Causing stomach upset - E320, E 338, E341, E465

Causing skin diseases - E320, E951

Causing intestinal upset - E627, E631

Conclusion: In conclusion, we have established that most food additives have a negative effect on the human body, affecting the organs and systems of the body. We recommend that you ignore attractive advertising campaigns for fast food products; You should choose your food carefully and not overdo it with food additives in order to protect your body from the atmospheric effects of food additives on the body.

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